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Estimating temperature in Fram Strait using DAMOCLES and ACOBAR acoustic tomography data by exploiting small-scale variability

by

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REPORT

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1 Introduction

The effects of the small-scale ocean variability in Fram Strait on the acoustic propagation there are now well documented. In the process of working through the acoustic forward problem to understand the nature of the tomography data acquired there, a more accurate approach to computing inverses of those data to obtain estimates for sound speed or temperature became apparent. This approach exploits the stochastic effects on the acoustic ray paths and travel times; inasmuch as it relies on the essential nature of the acoustic propagation it is an optimal approach to inverse estimates.

Although the steps to computing the inverses for Fram Strait are documented by existing recent publications in the major oceanographic journals, the precise formulations for the components of the inverses presently employed are separated in several of those publications. This report therefore brings these pieces together into a single document, while showing some of the details of the inverse estimates and documenting some of the results for each of the acoustic paths for which data are available. Much of the text in this report was copied wholesale from the publications, with only minor editing for consistency and clarity. The basic concepts of tomographic inverses are discussed by, among many others, [Cornuelle et al. \(1989\)](#), [Cornuelle et al. \(1993\)](#), [Munk, et al. \(1995\)](#), [Worcester \(2001\)](#), and, in the Fram Strait context, [Dushaw and Sagen \(2016\)](#).

The experiments in question are known as DAMOCLES (2008–2009) and ACOBAR (2010–2012) (Figure 1), and these experiments are documented in the publications listed below. This document does not seek to justify, explain, or interpret the steps of the analysis or their results. These essential aspects to the analysis are given in the publications listed below. This report merely just states the several precise details employed to obtain the inverse estimates. This report also cites only those works directly relevant to what is needed to compute the inverses; general supporting literature is cited in the publications.

In suggested order of study, the supporting publications are:

- Dushaw, B. D., Sagen, H., Beszczynska-Möller, A. (2016), Sound speed as a proxy variable for temperature in Fram Strait, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, **140**, 622–630, doi: 10.1121/1.4959000.

- Dushaw, B. D., and Sagen, H. (2016), A comparative study of the properties of moored/point and acoustic tomography/integral observations of Fram Strait using objective mapping techniques, *J. Ocean. Atmos. Tech.*, **33**, 2079–2093, doi: 10.1175/JTECH-D-15-0251.1.
- Dushaw, B. D., Sagen, H., and Beszczynska-Möller, A. (2016), On the effects of small-scale variability on acoustic propagation in Fram Strait: The tomography forward problem, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, **140**, 1286–1299, doi: 10.1121/1.4961207.
- Sagen, H., Dushaw, B. D., Skarsoulis, E. K., Dumont, D., Dzieciuch, M. A., Beszczynska-Möller, A. (2016), Time series of temperature in Fram Strait determined from the 2008–9 DAMOCLES acoustic tomography measurements and an ocean model, *J. Geophys. Res.*, **121**, doi: 10.1002/2015JC011591.
- Dushaw, B. D., and Sagen, H. (2017), The role of simulated small-scale ocean variability in inverse computations for ocean acoustic tomography, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, **142**, 3541–3552, doi: 10.1121/1.5016816.

Somewhat less relevant to the present analysis, but informative and useful:

- Sagen, H., Worcester, P. F., Dzieciuch, M. A., Geyer, F., Sandven, S., Babiker, M., Beszczynska-Möller, A., Dushaw, B. D., Cornuelle, B., (2017), Resolution, identification, and stability of broadband acoustic arrivals in Fram Strait, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, **141**, 2055–2068, doi: 10.1121/1.4978780.

Lastly, I would like to acknowledge that most everything I know about inverse estimates, with their sundry techniques, tricks, and pitfalls, I learned from Bruce Cornuelle during my student days at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography, 1987–1992.

2 Reference Ocean

As described in [Dushaw and Sagen \(2017\)](#) the reference ocean employed for the inverse consists of the sum of a climatological ocean derived from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) 2009 World Ocean Atlas (WOA09) and a simple empirical model for the small-scale thermal variations in Fram Strait. The small mesoscale variability was used to induce the apparent stochastic scattering as observed in the acoustics. These are discussed in turn.

2.1 Reference Ocean: Climatological Ocean

Climatological sound speed sections were computed from the temperature and salinity of the 2009 World Ocean Atlas (WOA09) ([Antonov, et al., 2010](#); [Locarnini, et al., 2010](#)). The Del Grosso sound speed equation was used throughout. Bathymetry along the acoustic path was derived from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean data base (IBCAO), with 2 min. resolution ([Jakobsson, et al., 2008](#)). Acoustic propagation in Fram Strait is bottom limited to around 2000 m, and on this section the depth varied from 1500 to 3000 m.

2.2 Reference Ocean: The Small-scale Contribution

Internal wave models failed to account for the high-frequency variations (greater than about 1 cpd) in sound speed, so an alternate interpretation for these variations

was required. Such variations are obviously not “dynamical,” that is, induced by vertical displacements, so we surmised they are advective in origin. Typical frequencies of the variations apparent in the Moored Array observations are 1–2 cpd. If a nominal barotropic current strength is about 10 cm s^{-1} , these temporal variations correspond to spatial variations of about 4–8 km, consistent with estimates for the expected Rossby radius. We therefore made the conjecture that the observed high-frequency variations were caused by the advection of small mesoscale features across the Moored Array mooring.

The ocean model used to construct realizations for the small mesoscale environment was similar to that used for ocean estimation by inverse of the acoustic travel times (Sagen, et al., 2016). A separate model was constructed for the “large” mesoscale (ca 10–20 km scales) environment for other purposes. The ocean variability was assumed to be separable into vertical and horizontal functions; the approach is objective mapping. The model was therefore composed of vertical modes and horizontal sinusoids,

$$F_S(r, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_V} V_i(z) [A_{i0}^0 + \sum_{j=1}^{N_H} (A_{ij}^1 \cos(K_j r) + A_{ij}^2 \sin(K_j r))] = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n P_n(r, z). \quad (1)$$

The vertical modes, $V_i(z)$, are empirical orthogonal functions (EOFs) of an ad hoc covariance matrix. For the small mesoscale environment, this matrix is composed of a full water column form

$$C(z_1, z_2) = 4e^{-\frac{sz}{550}} e^{-\frac{dz^2}{10sz}}, \quad (2)$$

where $sz = z_1 + z_2$ and $dz = z_1 - z_2$. This covariance was tuned to approximate the small-scale variability and covariance characteristics of Fram Strait. The vertical e-folding scale of variance, obtained by setting $z_1 = z_2$, is 275 m. Fifty vertical EOFs computed from a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of the covariance were used (e.g., Figure 2). Note that the vertical scales of the modeled variability are set by the scales of the vertical functions, not by the scale of this covariance.

As noted above, the Rossby radius of deformation is about 4–10 km in this region, and the horizontal scales of the simulated small mesoscale were assumed to be this size. These scales are not precise. Available hydrographic sections have not been obtained at sufficiently close intervals to accurately determine the statistics of the variability, certainly not at these small scales. Typical hydrographic profile spacing has been 18–20 km, comparable to the spacings of the AWI Moored Array.

The form for the wavenumber spectrum of horizontal variability employed here was

$$S_{ij} = \frac{w_i}{K_j^2 + K_{0i}^2} = \langle A_n^2 \rangle = W_n. \quad (3)$$

This form is derived from the assumption that the spatial covariance has an exponential falloff with range. The indexes i and j refer to vertical and horizontal function indexes. To account for the quite small scales, 1500 wavenumbers were employed, with $K_j = 2\pi j/L$ and L equal to 1.5 times the section range. The K_{0i} determine the horizontal scales associated with the i th vertical functions, with $K_{0i} = K_{10j+20}$. The form for the K_{0i} was determined in an ad hoc fashion to obtain a simulated variability that roughly approximates the O(4–8-km) expected length scales. Higher-order vertical EOFs have shorter scales. The W_n are the variances associated with the n th 2-D functions. The overall level of the wavenumber spectrum associated with each vertical function, w_i , is set by the EOF spectrum.

Using the variances of the amplitudes determined by the EOF and wavenumber spectra, statistically-consistent snapshots of the small mesoscale ocean were readily derived.

Mesoscale snapshots were derived using amplitudes for the 2-D functions given by

$$A_n = \sqrt{W_n} p_n \quad (4)$$

where p_n is a random number with Gaussian distribution and unit standard deviation. The computed amplitudes, A_n , were then applied to each 2-D function in the equation for $F_S(r, z)$ above to obtain simulated snapshots of small-scale ocean states.

The lower middle panel of Figure 3 gives an example of the small mesoscale environment modeled this way. The simulated sound speed variations ($\pm 6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) are roughly consistent with the high-frequency variations observed by the Moored Array.

3 Quantification of Travel Time Differences

The general approach was to randomly assign rays to measured peak arrivals, without regard to specific identification, but a well-defined prescription for making these assignments was required. Care was taken to ensure the ray assignments were not biased in some way, and such a prescription may be required for employing this data type for data assimilation. The ray path-to-peak assignment also gives the difference between measured and computed travel times, the quantity required for obtaining the temperature estimates from these data. Employing trial and error, several schemes for peak identification were developed; the prescription described here appeared to work well.

First, the arrival peaks occurring within the main pulse were selected. Bottom reflected arrivals and later scattered arrivals were ignored here. Peaks arriving too early or too late to possibly be within the main pulse were omitted. Under the assumption that the peak with the largest amplitude occurs within the main pulse, travel times arriving earlier or later than 150 ms from this largest-peak travel time were then excluded. With these criteria, only peaks within the main pulse remained. The remaining peaks were then sorted by amplitude.

To obtain the computed ray paths and travel times to be associated with a particular acoustic transmission, a full set of eigenrays was first computed using the reference ocean. The computed rays were then sorted by absolute value of the ray angle at the source, smallest to largest. This sorting was to alleviate a suspected issue with bias; a systematic identification of rays with one portion of the main arrival pulse might bias the inverse estimates. The aim of sorting the rays by angle was to introduce an element of randomness with the identifications within the pulse, while making the assumption that the rays with the smallest angles travel closest to the sound channel axis and have the largest amplitudes. If there were N measured peaks found from the measured main arrival pulse, sorted by amplitude from largest to smallest, then these were assigned to N computed rays, sorted by source angle from smallest to largest. The unstable nature of the ray calculations resulting from the sound speed environment (Dushaw, et al., 2016b) contributed to the randomness of the ray assignments; this property is exploited in this case. Five to ten peaks were selected from each hydrophone record, roughly the nominal number of available peaks. The DAMOCLES estimates used data from 4 hydrophones, so about twenty data were employed for each of those inverses. One potential refinement of this prescription would be to use as much data as possible from each transmission, while guarding against biasing effects. Abandoning specific, selected peaks as the data and using the continuous arrival pulse in some way, would be helpful in this regard.

Given the general imprecision, or looseness, of this procedure, travel time uncertainties of about 100 ms were assumed for the travel time data. This uncertainty is large compared to the usual $O(10 \text{ ms})$ uncertainty when individual rays are resolved. Individual travel times, or, more precisely, the differences between computed and measured travel times, are only accurate to within the $O(100 \text{ ms})$ width of the main arrival pulse. The accuracy of the inverse estimates rely on the large numbers of data and their random element to overwhelm the large uncertainties assigned to the individual travel times.

To be as realistic as possible, a new reference ocean and set of ray paths should be computed for each inverse or transmission. The repeated computation of the ray paths is challenging, however. While any particular ray computation takes just a few minutes, such ray computations would be required for each of the $O(1000)$ available transmissions associated with each 250-day time series. Since only $O(10)$ peak travel time data are available from each hydrophone record and transmission, while $O(500)$ rays are available from a single ray computation using the reference ocean, an expedient is apparent. The forward problem operator, G , required for the inverse, was computed using the complete set of $O(500)$ rays from a single reference ocean. The values for this matrix together with the ray travel times then formed a pool with population $O(500)$ from which the small number of values required for the data used each inverse were selected at random. After the reference ocean was corrected by the inverse, ray computations were used to verify the solutions agreed with data, however. Even relying on the single, initial ray trace, the computations of the inverse estimates and associated ray travel times for a 250-day time series took about 2 days on a high-end personal computer.

4 The Inverse Model

The inverse of tomography travel times to obtain sound speed estimates has been described many times using a weighted least squares fit of a particular model, and associated data and model parameter statistics, to the travel time data. The details of the inverse will not be repeated here. The particular parameterized model employed for the present inverse is repeated here, however. The ocean model used to fit the tomography data consisted of a truncated Fourier series, that is sines and cosines, in the horizontal and a small set of empirical vertical functions.

For the ocean model in this study, we assumed the horizontal and vertical variability were separable. That is, if $F(r, z)$ is the ocean state of a scalar variable such as sound speed or temperature to be estimated, then it can be modeled as a linear superposition of two-dimensional (2-D) functions of range r and depth z ,

$$F(r, z) = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n P_n(r, z) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_V} \sum_{j=1}^{N_H} A_{ij} V_i(z) H_j(r) \quad (5)$$

where the sums are over the vertical (i) and horizontal (j) indexes. A_{ij} is the amplitude associated with the i th vertical function and j th horizontal function. It is certainly possible to avoid this assumption by devising sets of 2-D functions that might accurately model the ocean. Such functions might be 2-D EOFs, for example, derived from estimates of the 2-D covariance of the ocean. The separability assumption simplifies matters considerably without adversely affecting the ocean model estimates.

The horizontal variability was assumed to be composed of the linear superposition of sinusoids, $\sin(K_j r)$ and $\cos(K_j r)$, that is, horizontal variability was modeled using a truncated Fourier series. While more sophisticated horizontal functions are certainly

possible, e.g., horizontal modes tuned to describe the horizontal variations of the west Spitzbergen Current, sines and cosines can accurately account for horizontal variability in most situations. (A truncated Fourier series may not be an appropriate model for sharp ocean fronts). The wavenumbers, $K_j = \frac{2\pi j}{1.5L}$, where L is the range of the Fram Strait section. In defining the wavenumbers, this length is increased by a factor of 1.5 to avoid the periodicity effects at the ends of the section. If there are N_V vertical functions and N_H wavenumbers, then a total of $N = N_V(2N_H + 1)$ 2-D functions comprise the ocean model. With the model employed here, N_V was 5, while N_H was 10, giving a total of 105 2-D functions.

4.1 Vertical Functions.

The vertical functions employed in an objective map require careful consideration. Any estimate for sound speed variability should minimize unrealistic vertical gradients. Acoustic propagation is governed by these gradients, and unphysical discontinuities in the estimated sound speeds can render the acoustic predictions unphysical.

Information on the nature of the variability in the vertical in Fram Strait was determined from a variety of sources, including the Moored Array data, glider data, CTD data, and the results of a regional high-resolution numerical ocean model (HYCOM) for Fram Strait computed by the Nansen Center modeling group (Sagen, et al., 2016). No single parameterized model could encompass all of the variances, length scales, and other properties suggested by these sources. The ultimate vertical parameterization was obtained by approximating the variance as a function of depth and vertical correlation length to be similar to Fram Strait variability. In particular, the variances as a function of depth assumed for this study are similar to those observed by the Moored Array (Dushaw, et al., 2016b). There are many possibilities for the vertical functions such as baroclinic modes, layers, or the direct value at particular depths. In cases where acoustics are employed, it is important to model vertical variability such that large sound speed gradients are avoided, unless there are compelling reasons to include such gradients, e.g., a known mixed layer. EOFs for the vertical variability derived from either data or numerical ocean models are smoothly varying functions that work well for acoustics. The vertical functions employed for this study were EOFs of a synthetic covariance function. If $sz = z_1 + z_2$ and $dz = z_1 - z_2$, then the (symmetric) synthetic covariance was given by

$$C(z_1, z_2) = 20e^{\frac{-sz}{750}} e^{\frac{-dz^2}{100sz}} \quad (6)$$

In this model, the variance of sound speed at the surface was assumed to be about $20 \text{ (m s}^{-1}\text{)}^2$, and the e-folding scale of variance with depth is 350 m (Figure 2). This covariance was subsequently adjusted near the surface, however. The variances within 40 m of the surface were increased in an ad hoc fashion to model the ubiquitous, near-surface mixed layer found in Fram Strait. This increase is evident in the variance near the surface in the left panel of Figure 2; its specific form was $\sqrt{1 + 2 \cdot (1 - \tanh(0 : .2 : 5))}$, corresponding to depths from 0 to 250 m at 10 m intervals. With this form, the surface value of the covariance was increased by a factor 1.73^2 . The singular value decomposition of this covariance gives the EOFs that model the vertical variability (Figure 2). The spectrum of the EOF eigenvalues $\{E_i\}$ specify the variance of each EOF to be used for the objective map.

EOFs such as these form a general basis set of functions for fitting variability in the vertical. The aim is to fit such variability while enforcing a covariance similar to that

that is observed in the ocean, viz., greater variance toward the surface, greater vertical scales deeper down. While EOFs derived strictly from a suitable comprehensive data set, should one be available, would fit variability in the vertical optimally, in practice EOFs derived from any reasonable covariance can fit such variability well. Insofar as acoustics are concerned, the principal advantage of an analytic approach is that EOFs defined this way are smooth and well-behaved, whereas EOFs derived from covariances computed strictly from data can have artificial gradients or glitches stemming from the realities of ocean data.

4.2 Wavenumber Spectrum.

Simple sines and cosines of a truncated Fourier series were used to model variability in the horizontal. The form for the wavenumber spectrum, which sets the assumed length scales and gives the weights for these functions, was

$$S_{ij} = \frac{w_i}{X_i} \frac{1}{K_j^2 + K_{0i}^2} \quad (7)$$

where indexes i and j refer to vertical and horizontal function indexes. The wavenumbers, $K_j = \frac{2\pi j}{1.5L}$, where L is DAMOCLES tomography path length; this length is multiplied by 1.5 to minimize periodicity effects on the solution. X_i sets the horizontal scale of the i th vertical function, and $K_{0i} = \frac{2\pi}{X_i}$. The values for the X_i were $X_1 = 200$ km, $X_2 = 100$ km, $X_3 = 50$ km, $X_4 = 30$ km, and $X_5 = 10$ km. The horizontal length scale is shorter for higher-order vertical functions. As described by (Dushaw and Sagen, 2016; Dushaw, et al., 2016b), the w_i were set by the spectrum of the vertical functions.

This model (vertical functions, truncated Fourier series in the horizontal, associated model variances) was used to fit the acoustic travel time data using the stochastic inverse. The prior weights of the model parameters, that is, the assumed the variances of the model parameters, A_{ij} , are an essential component of the ocean model. These weights were defined by the wavenumber spectra.

5 Inverse Procedure

The steps to computing an inverse of the Fram Strait tomography data and subsequent temperature estimate are:

1. Compute climatological sound speed and obtain a climatological sound speed section along the acoustic path at ca. 20 km intervals.
2. Compute a stochastic mesoscale realization for the acoustic path, as prescribed above and form the reference ocean as the sum of climatological and mesoscale environments. The reference sound speed section is

$$c(r, z) = c_0(r, z) + F_S(r, z) \quad (8)$$

3. Compute acoustic ray travel times and paths for this section between the source and receiver. Separate ray computations are required for each depth for which there are receivers. Use rays that do not interact with the sea floor. Rays were computed using initial ray angles between -8 and 8 degrees. Some 500–600 rays are usually obtained to each receiver as a consequence of the mesoscale variability and background sound speed profile.

4. The forward problem matrix, or operator, \mathbf{G} , is computed as the integral over the ray paths of the 2-D model functions,

$$G_{ij} = -2 \int_{\Gamma_i} \frac{P_j(r, z)}{c_0^2(r, z)} ds \quad (9)$$

where Γ_j are a set of acoustic ray paths and $c_0(r, z)$ is the reference sound speed section. This integral is computed for all ca. 500 rays obtained.

5. Select 5–10 of the largest peaks from within the main pulse of an arrival pattern of a transmission to use as data.
6. Randomly select 5–10 of the predicted ray travel times and their associated forward problem matrix from the “pool” of ca. 500 available.
7. Randomly match the predicted travel times to the measured peak travel times, together with the associated forward problem matrix elements.
8. Compute inverse to solve for the amplitudes, \hat{A}_j (the hat denotes estimated values) of the $P_j(r, z)$, using 100 ms as the data uncertainty. The data used for the inverse are the measured travel times less the predicted travel times. In matrix notation where matrices are bold font,

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{GA} + \epsilon \quad (10)$$

where ϵ is the data uncertainty (actually a covariance, but assumed diagonal).

9. Compute the corrected sound speed section,

$$c(r, z) = c_0(r, z) + F_S(r, z) + \delta c(r, z) \quad (11)$$

where

$$\delta c(r, z) = \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{A}_j P_j(r, z). \quad (12)$$

6 Testing the Solution

The inverse solution itself can be tested by a variety of internal statistical checks, the misfit relative to the assumed data uncertainties being one of them. The details of the solutions themselves are perhaps less important, inasmuch as the intention is to compute range- and depth-averaged sound speed or temperature. These averages are the primary reliable information to be derived from these data.

The ultimate test of the solution is to retrace the rays through the corrected sound speed section and compare the new travel times to the data. In the computation for the inverse, this step is the most time consuming. While any particular ray trace at these ranges takes at most a few minutes, there are $O(1000)$ transmissions, hence $O(1000)$ ray traces must be computed. One factor is that the ray traces with the small-scale structure take quite a bit longer to complete. In any case, as shown in Figures 4–19 the inverse as described here and in [Dushaw and Sagen \(2017\)](#) results in sound speed sections for which the distribution of ray travel times agree with the observations. For this comparison, ray travel times are selected in the same manner as they are prior to the inverse. For expediency, the procedure implemented was to add the range-average sound speed profile to the reference, rather than the estimated sound speed section.

Although they are mostly unphysical, maps of the corrections to the sound speed section can be readily computed as $F(r, z)$ above using the solutions for $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$, as noted above. Examples of such results are shown in Figures 20–23. Such estimates can be misleading, however, since the acoustic data do not have sufficient constraint on the details of these sections, see [Dushaw and Sagen \(2016\)](#) (Figure 12 of that paper). The perturbations themselves are nearly dwarfed by the estimated uncertainties, show in the lower panels of Figures 20–23. The uncertainties are actually the diagonal of the error covariance, hence the uncertainty maps show only a small fraction of the information within the error covariance. The tomography constrains the average, hence the off-diagonal components of the error covariance are important, as has been stressed countless times. The computations of maps such as Figures 20–23 are primarily diagnostics (a sanity check) to verify that the bookkeeping of the various matrices used for the inverse has not gone astray. Note that the acoustic data were obtained between the 0 and ca. 302 km ranges, so outside of these ranges the solution relaxes back to the prior - even larger uncertainty values and estimated sound speed perturbation decreasing to zero.

The estimate for the horizontal average is also readily computed, together with its uncertainty, and these are shown in the right panels of Figures 20–23. The uncertainties are considerably smaller than for the section estimate, but they are still large. The solution appears to go to zero at depth, but there is a small but non-zero variance assumed at depth for these solutions.

Ultimately, any inverse of acoustic data for an ocean estimate has two basic goals: (1) to obtain a realization for the ocean (by any means) for which computed arrival coda agree with the observations, and (2) an estimate for the uncertainty of that ocean realization. The inverses described here accomplish these basic goals.

7 Computing Range- and Depth-Average Sound Speed or Temperature

The range average computation is briefly introduced above. The average quantities are the best resolved estimates, that is, they have quite small uncertainties. These averages are computed not in physical space, but in model space. The reason is that the averages of the $P_n(r, z)$ in equation (5) can be computed directly, and those averages can be directly applied to the \mathbf{A} . The depth averages of the vertical functions were computed numerically, while the horizontal averages of the sines and cosines were computed analytically. Computing averages can thus avoid any foray into physical space, hence the matrix dimensions can remain small. Computing average estimates is thus quite fast and efficient.

As noted by ([Dushaw, et al., 2016b](#)), the ray sampling in Fram Strait is mostly in the upper 1000 m of ocean, hence averages were computed over this depth range. Typical formal uncertainties for the range- and depth-average temperature were 30 – 70 $m^\circ\text{C}$. Rays do often extend deeper than 1000 m, meaning some estimated ocean variability may actually be occurring deeper than 1000 m. Accounting for this situation is the role of the inverse - such ambiguities are meant to be incorporated naturally into the uncertainty estimates. It therefore goes without saying that the whole process only has integrity if the prior ocean model and associated variances are consistent with the actual ocean variability.

8 Conversion of Sound Speed Estimates to Temperature Estimates

The estimates for sound speed can be accurately converted to temperature estimates; salinity variations do not significantly affect the estimates of sound speed. In the Fram Strait region the factor $4.5 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ can be used to scale between sound speed and temperature estimates with an accuracy of perhaps 2% (Dushaw, et al., 2016a). The uncertainty of the average over depth and range is small (Dushaw and Sagen, 2016); the oceanographically meaningful quantity is the average. To obtain an estimate of temperature, therefore, the appropriate average sound speed quantity is calculated, and this quantity and its uncertainty were scaled to obtain temperature.

The time series of estimated, averaged sound speed or temperature is noisy. The noise of the time series reflects the scattered nature of the travel time peaks within the wide arrival pulse, together with the looseness of the inversion with its large data uncertainties and approximate ray identification. The high-frequency noise, with rapid variations from transmission to transmission, should be distinguished from the apparent variations in temperature as a result of mesoscale variability occurring at weekly to monthly time scales. The former is noise, the latter is signal. The uncertainties of the temperature estimates are dominated by the high-frequency noise of the time series, rather than the formally-estimated inverse uncertainties. The formal inverse uncertainties for the range- and depth averages are about 0.27 m s^{-1} ($60 \text{ m}^\circ\text{C}$). The root-mean-square (RMS) noise of the time series, estimated by subtracting a 2-day running mean of the time series, is 0.43 m s^{-1} ($96 \text{ m}^\circ\text{C}$).

The time series of absolute temperature is estimated from the sound speed estimates with a series of simple calculations. These calculations convert sound speed fluctuations relative to the time-mean sound speed to temperature fluctuations relative to the time-mean temperature. The corrected estimates are first used to obtain a time series of absolute sound speed, averaged over range and 0–1000 m depth. The time-mean sound speed is subtracted, and the estimated variations in sound speed are then scaled by a factor $4.5 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ (Dushaw, et al., 2016a) to obtain the estimated variations in temperature. The corrected time-mean temperature is obtained by first computing the range- and depth-averaged temperature of the reference ocean (the World Ocean Atlas). This mean is corrected according to the difference between the time means of reference and estimated sound speeds. The climatology is slightly warmer than the DAMOCLES or ACOBAR measurements. The corrected mean temperature is then added to the time series of estimated temperature variations to give the estimates for absolute temperature of Figures 24–28.

9 A Smoothed Estimate for the Time Series

The inverse estimates for temperature are shown in the red dots of Figures 24–28. These estimates have considerable scatter, consistent with the nature of the acoustic data we have available. There are typically 8 estimates per day, however, so we may compute a smoothed estimate for temperature that will combine many temperature estimates and reduce the uncertainty.

An optimal choice for a smoother is not obvious. On the one hand the data are rather noisy, as just noted, while on the other hand the basic time series in temperature is also quite variable, showing large jumps from week to week. The transmission-to-

transmission scatter of the data is not physical, since it just corresponds to the width of the acoustic pulse and the scatter of the acoustic arrival peaks that were obtained from each transmission. The week-to-week jumps are physical, however, and they correspond to the small-scale variability that is regularly advecting across the acoustic path. The acoustic paths are evidently not sufficiently long enough to average the “mesoscale” variability. It seems clear that a running mean or other such filter would not be appropriate, since such filters would essentially combine data from different ocean states.

In the end, I chose to use a weighted least-squares cubic spline fit to obtain a sensible low-frequency estimate for the temperature time series. The matlab routine `lsspl.m`, developed by R. Parker and M. Dzieciuch at the Institute of Geophysics and Planetary Physics (IGPP/SIO), was used for this purpose; it implements a weighted least-squares fit as described by [de Boor \(2001\)](#). A sequence of fits were made, first a loose fit to identify and remove obvious outliers (deviating from the fit by more than 3.5 standard deviations), then a tighter fit to remove additional outliers (deviating by more than 2.5 standard deviations), then a final fit to only the good data points. Typically about 10% of the data were identified as outliers. Curiously, the values for the final RMS misfits were about the same value as the formal inverse uncertainty estimates, though the two have no real direct relation.

The least-squares fit requires values for the data uncertainties and for the upper bound on the squared-weighted misfit (“ χ squared”). These values were the RMS of the misfit and the length of the time series (one standard deviation average misfit), respectively. While these are sensible values, they were ultimately selected so as to give a subjectively satisfying fit to the temperature time series. The weighted least-squares cubic spline fits are the blue lines in Figures 24–28.

One downside to this approach is that an estimate for the uncertainty of the temperature values of the cubic spline fit was not readily apparent. One sensible estimate may be to assume that each point of the cubic spline fit is employing about two days of temperature data, or 16 data points. If the RMS misfit of the data to the fit is about 80 m°C, then the uncertainty of the fitted time series is $80/\sqrt{16} = 20$ m°C. As noted by [Dushaw and Sagen \(2017\)](#), such values are so small as to be negligible for most applications.

10 Supporting DAMOCLES and ACOBAR NERSC Reports

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Requests for the acoustic data described in this report should be made to Dr. Hanne Sagen at the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center in Bergen, Norway, web: www.nersc.no, email: hanne.sagen@nersc.no.

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13 FIGURES

Figure 1. The ACOBAR observing array (magenta, black) and DAMOCLES path (blue). Mooring C failed to transmit and was not recovered, so no data were available from the black segments. The sound speed at 250 m depth on Yearday 192, 2003 was derived from the Estimating the Circulation and Climate of the Ocean, Phase II (ECCO2) project ocean state estimates. ECCO2 was a global numerical model for the temporal evolution of ocean temperature, salinity, currents, etc. at 1/4 degree resolution fit to a wide range of available ocean data and forcing using data assimilation. Warm, salty water from the North Atlantic is transported along the west coast of Svalbard through Fram Strait. Azimuthal equal area projection.

Figure 2. (left) The variance of sound speed (heavy black line) as a function of depth assumed for the ocean model. The solid and dashed lines indicate the covariance functions with respect to the starred points along the variance line. These variances and depth scales are roughly in accordance with the nature of the ocean determined from a variety of data. (right) The empirical orthogonal functions of this covariance are the vertical functions used for the ocean model (solid line is EOF 1).

Figure 3. (bottom) The reference sound speed section for computing inversions of Fram Strait tomography data obtained along the ACOBAR A to B path. Greenland is to the right, Svalbard to the left. The reference consists of the sum of (top) the 2009 World Ocean Atlas sound speed and (middle) a simulation of small mesoscale variability tuned to available observations. The contributions of the small scale variability to sound speed are essential to understanding acoustic propagation in the region.

Figure 4. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings A and B. The color indicates arrival angle (negative angle rays are mostly masked by positive angle rays), while the dot size indicates signal-to-noise ratio. The top panel shows the reference ocean travel times as the red dots, while the bottom panel shows the travel times computed using the inverse solution as the magenta dots. Adding a representation of small-scale fluctuations to the smooth World Ocean Atlas gives reference-ocean travel times that more closely resemble the data. The many rays obtained from the fluctuating reference ocean can be exploited to compute an accurate inverse estimate.

Figure 5. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings A and B. As in Figure 4.

Figure 6. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings A and Da. As in Figure 4.

Figure 7. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings A and Da. As in Figure 4.

Figure 8. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings A and Db. As in Figure 4.

Figure 9. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings A and Db. As in Figure 4.

Figure 10. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings B and A. As in Figure 4.

Figure 11. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings B and A. As in Figure 4.

Figure 12. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings B and Da. As in Figure 4.

Figure 13. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings B and Da. As in Figure 4.

Figure 14. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings B and Db. As in Figure 4.

Figure 15. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the ACOBAR project in 2010–2011 along the zonal path between moorings B and Db. As in Figure 4.

Figure 16. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the DAMOCLES project in 2008–2009 along the single path to receiver 1.

Figure 17. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the DAMOCLES project in 2008–2009 along the single path to receiver 2.

Figure 18. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the DAMOCLES project in 2008–2009 along the single path to receiver 3.

Figure 19. Time series of acoustic travel times obtained by the DAMOCLES project in 2008–2009 along the single path to receiver 4.

Figure 21. Example of a sound speed section and its uncertainty computed from acoustic data obtained on the ACOBAR A to B path. The yearday is noted in the central panel. The lower panel shows the estimated uncertainty for the section, without indicating the importance of the off-diagonal elements of the covariance. The right panel shows the range average of the section and its estimated uncertainty.

Figure 22. Example of a sound speed section and its uncertainty computed from acoustic data obtained on the ACOBAR A to B path. The yearday is noted in the central panel. The lower panel shows the estimated uncertainty for the section, without indicating the importance of the off-diagonal elements of the covariance. The right panel shows the range average of the section and its estimated uncertainty.

Figure 23. Example of a sound speed section and its uncertainty computed from acoustic data obtained on the ACOBAR A to B path. The yearday is noted in the central panel. The lower panel shows the estimated uncertainty for the section, without indicating the importance of the off-diagonal elements of the covariance. The right panel shows the range average of the section and its estimated uncertainty.

Figure 24. Range- and depth-averaged temperature along the 302-km path ACOBAR A to B path. Depth average is over the depth interval 0 to 1000 m, which is the dominant sampling interval of the ray paths. Individual estimates are denoted by the red dots, while the blue line is a weighted cubic spline fit to those estimates. The formal inverse uncertainty for this average is about $75 \text{ m}^\circ\text{C}$, as indicated. Dates at the start and end of each time series are indicated, while the red lines indicate the equivalent average in the WOA09.

Figure 25. Range- and depth-averaged temperature along the 182-km path ACOBAR A to D path. Depth average is over the depth interval 0 to 1000 m, which is the dominant sampling interval of the ray paths. Individual estimates are denoted by the red dots, while the blue line is a weighted cubic spline fit to those estimates. The formal inverse uncertainty for this average is about $75 \text{ m}^\circ\text{C}$, as indicated. Dates at the start and end of each time series are indicated, while the red lines indicate the equivalent average in the WOA09.

Figure 26. Range- and depth-averaged temperature along the 302-km path ACOBAR B to A path. Depth average is over the depth interval 0 to 1000 m, which is the dominant sampling interval of the ray paths. Individual estimates are denoted by the red dots, while the blue line is a weighted cubic spline fit to those estimates. The formal inverse uncertainty for this average is about $75 \text{ m}^\circ\text{C}$, as indicated. Dates at the start and end of each time series are indicated, while the red lines indicate the equivalent average in the WOA09.

Figure 27. Range- and depth-averaged temperature along the 302-km path ACOBAR B to D path. Depth average is over the depth interval 0 to 1000 m, which is the dominant sampling interval of the ray paths. Individual estimates are denoted by the red dots, while the blue line is a weighted cubic spline fit to those estimates. The formal inverse uncertainty for this average is about 75 m°C, as indicated. Dates at the start and end of each time series are indicated, while the red lines indicate the equivalent average in the WOA09.

Figure 28. Range- and depth-averaged temperature along the 130-km path DAMOCLES path. Depth average is over the depth interval 0 to 1000 m, which is the dominant sampling interval of the ray paths. Individual estimates are denoted by the red dots, while the blue line is a weighted cubic spline fit to those estimates. The formal inverse uncertainty for this average is about 75 m°C, as indicated. Dates at the start and end of each time series are indicated, while the red lines indicate the equivalent average in the WOA09. Equivalent temperature estimates derived from hydrographic sections are indicated by the black dots; the error bars indicate data RMS.